

McDonagh'ın Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri (2017) Filminde Feminist Mekânsal Direniş

Feminist Spatial Resistance in McDonagh's Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri (2017)

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the struggle of the female protagonist, Mildred Hayes, in Martin McDonagh's *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017) through the lens of feminist spatial resistance, emplacement, and displacement. The film explores how Mildred constructs her identity as a woman and a mother, confronts her past, and resists social pressures, all within the spatial dynamics of a small Missouri town. Central to the narrative is how she transforms her anger into political expression through the "language of billboards" and develops a form of resistance against patriarchal hegemony. Through this, Mildred creates a spatial "female language," shifting from a grieving and silenced mother into an active and outspoken rebel who claims visibility in the public sphere. Within this framework, the film's feminist practices of emplacement and displacement are examined through feminist spatial theories, which reveal the social, affective, and embodied dimensions of space. The article views Mildred's effort to reposition herself within patriarchal structures as a disruptive act and explores her transformation into a woman and mother who can speak, act, and create her own language. Ultimately, Mildred Hayes's intervention in patriarchal spaces is interpreted as a form of feminist resistance. Through this intervention, the female protagonist's potential to create an alternative social order within existing spatial structures also becomes visible.

Keywords: Martin McDonagh, Feminism, Gender, Ecriture Feminine, Spatial Resistance

ÖZ

Bu makale, Martin McDonagh'ın *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017) filmindeki kadın kahraman Mildred Hayes'in mücadelesini feminist mekânsal direniş, konumlandırma ve yersizleştirme perspektifinden incelemektedir. Film, Mildred'ın kadın ve anne kimliğini inşa etme, geçmişle yüzleşme ve toplumsal baskılara karşı direnme sürecini, küçük bir Missouri kasabesindeki hikâyesi üzerinden mekânsal politikalarla ilişkilendirerek ele alır. Karakterin "reklam panosu dili" aracılığıyla öfkesini siyasal bir söyleme dönüştürmesi ve ataerkil hegemonya karşısında geliştirdiği direniş, anlatının merkezinde konumlanır. Böylece Mildred, mekânsal bağlamda kurduğu "kadın dili" sayesinde yas tutan ve susturulmuş bir anneden, kamusal alanda görünürlük kazanan ve söz talep eden aktif bir isyancıya dönüşür. Bu bağlamda filmdeki feminist konumlandırma ve yersizleştirme pratikleri, feminist mekân kuramlarıyla birlikte mekânın toplumsal, duysal ve deneyimsel boyutlarını odağına alan eleştirel yaklaşımlar doğrultusunda değerlendirilecektir. Çalışma, Mildred'in ataerkil yapılar içerisinde kendini konumlandırma çabasını yıkıcı bir eylem biçimi olarak ele almakta ve onu konuşabilen, hareket edebilen ve kendi dilini kurabilen bir kadın ve anne figürüne nasıl dönüştüğünü tartışmayı amaçlamaktadır. Sonuç olarak, Mildred Hayes'in ataerkil mekânlara yönelik müdahalesi, feminist bir direniş biçimi olarak okunmaktadır. Bu müdahale aracılığıyla da kadın kahramanın mevcut mekânsal yapılar içinde alternatif bir toplumsal düzen yaratma potansiyeli görünür kılınmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Martin McDonagh, Feminizm, Toplumsal Cinsiyet Politikası, Kadın Dili, Mekânsal Direniş

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INTRODUCTION

“The very act of naming has been till now a male prerogative, and how we can begin to see and name--and therefore live—afresh” (Adrienne Rich, 1979, p. 28)

“Representation of the world, like the world itself, is the work of men; they describe it from their own point of view, which they confuse with the absolute truth” (Simone de Beauvoir, 1953, p. 172)

Irish-British playwright and filmmaker Martin McDonagh's *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017) explores the portrayal of female grief and anger through feminist spatial protest. The story follows Mildred Hayes (starring Frances McDormand), a working-class mother in a small Southern town in Missouri, who takes an unconventional step to demand justice after her daughter Angela's unsolved rape and murder. Seven months after the crime, Mildred rents three billboards at the town's edge and, via the use of billboards, she displays questions that remain unanswered: “How Come, Chief Willoughby?” “And Still No Arrests?” and “Raped While Dying” (06:58). In the film, these questions do more than challenge authority by breaking the town's silence. The female protagonist refuses to mourn quietly or conform to socially accepted behaviors, thereby challenging traditional roles that expect women's pain to stay hidden. By expressing her rage publicly, she pushes the boundaries of how women are expected to move, speak, and feel in public space. Following this confrontation, the billboards she rents symbolize feminist resistance that echoes feminist philosopher Hélène Cixous's idea of “écriture féminine.” In her essay, “The Laugh of the Medusa” (1976), Cixous argues that a woman “must put herself into the text—as into the world and into history—by her own movement” (p. 875). Through the billboards, the female protagonist in the film inscribes her pain into public space, refusing silence and making her grief visible and undeniable.

In order to understand the spatial and political significance of Mildred's protest in *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017), the ideas of feminist geographers such as Doreen Massey and Linda McDowell, and spatial theorists including Henri Lefebvre and Yi-Fu Tuan, offer a useful critical lens. Mildred's roadside protest, then, can be situated within a broader feminist tradition that, since the 19th century, has challenged the notion that women have a “proper place.” As feminist thinkers Adrienne Rich and Simone de Beauvoir have argued, the power to name and represent the world has historically been monopolized by men. In response, feminist theory has worked to dismantle these hierarchies by revealing how space itself, often assumed to be neutral, functions to reproduce the distinction between public and private spheres. This idea, that space is socially produced and shaped by patriarchal power, is further related to Henri Lefebvre's (1976) assertion that “space is political and ideological” (p. 31). Even though Lefebvre approaches space from a different theoretical tradition, his view of its ideological nature intersects meaningfully with feminist critiques. Thus, both claims have inspired feminist geographers, including Doreen Massey and Linda McDowell, to expose how spatial control is associated with control over women's voices, behaviors, and identities. In light of these insights, the public sphere has been interpreted as more than a physical environment but as a space of struggle where women are excluded, limited, and sometimes held back. When confined to domestic roles, women are denied full participation in public life, which limits their identity and agency (Massey, 1994, p. 179). Considering how women move through space and how that movement is so often limited, it is hard not to recall Virginia Woolf's (1977) famous call for “a room of one's own,” indicating “a place a woman must have [...] if she is to write fiction”

(p. 7). Woolf's room, after all, is more than a metaphor for creativity. It is also a pause in movement where women can think freely and turn the stillness into meaning. In this sense, a point made by humanistic geographer Yi-Fu Tuan (1977) offers a way to understand the relation between self-expression and emplacement in public space: "if we think of space as that which allows movement, then place is pause; each pause in movement makes it possible for location to be transformed into place" (p. 6). His theory speaks to feminist concerns, particularly when related to Doreen Massey's (1994) assertion that "the limitation of women's mobility, in terms both of identity and space, has been in some cultural contexts a crucial means of subordination" (p. 179). It becomes clear, then, that the places women inhabit or are kept away from are not just physical locations. They are equally about what women *are allowed to* express once they gain access to these places. As Linda McDowell (1999) points out, the idea of women having a particular "place" in society is built into varied social layers from family structures to institutions of power (p. 12). However, a woman's subversion in terms of placement explains why a woman raising her voice in public, especially against authority, feels like an act of defiance. bell hooks (2014) captures this with salient clarity when she writes, "moving from silence into speech is [...] a gesture of defiance that heals, that makes new life and new growth possible" (p. 9). In McDonagh's film, the billboards leave us with the image of divergence in which a woman's words, set against the road, refuse to disappear, claiming (re)placement at the cost of otherization and alienation.

This article, through the lens of feminist politics and spatiality, turns to Martin McDonagh's *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017) to explore how one woman, Mildred Hayes, interrupts the expected flow of space, place, and power in her small town, Missouri. Although the film is not explicitly feminist, it raises powerful questions about what it means for a woman to claim space and what it might cost her to be heard in public. In doing so, the film ultimately circles back to the fundamental dilemma posed at the outset: Can a woman speak? And, how far is her presence heard in the public space? In order to explore this problem, the article proceeds in three parts. The first part outlines feminist spatiality, particularly drawing on the theories of Henri Lefebvre, Yi-Fu Tuan, Doreen Massey, Linda McDowell, and Hélène Cixous. The second part turns to McDonagh's theatrical background, including a summary of the film itself. Finally, the third part provides a close reading of the protagonist, Mildred Hayes's spatial tactics in the film, analyzing how her public interventions challenge gendered expectations of visibility, silence, and action.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND: GENDERED SPACES

The concepts of "space" and "place" are fundamental to our understanding of everyday life. Whether consciously or unconsciously, we rely on these notions to describe physical surroundings or convey our subjective experiences. However, although inextricably linked, each notion embodies distinct meanings. In literary theory, while place has often been framed as a more subjective concept, related to personal experiences and familiarity, space has been viewed as an abstract notion that gives us a sense of vastness and freedom. As geographer Yi-Fu Tuan (1977) briefly puts it, "place is security, space is freedom: we are attached to the one and long for the other" (p. 3). He elaborates that "what begins as undifferentiated space becomes place as we get to know it better and endow it with value" (p. 6). On the other hand, Henri Lefebvre conceptualizes this distinction through social relations. In *The Production of Space* (1991), Lefebvre discusses space on three levels: perceived, conceived, and lived (p. 288). When a park or a street appears as a design on a map, it is a "conceived space." When people walk through it or use it in daily life, it becomes a perceived space, which is something experienced physically. When personal memories, such as playing games as a child, come into play, they transform into a

"lived space." Yet, for Lefebvre, this process is not only about personal experiences and familiarity. For him (1991), space is political where power, ideology, and social relations are "produced and reproduced" (p. 77) through which authority is reinforced. In this sense, space is shaped by those who plan, regulate, and inhabit it as a "means of control, and hence of domination, of power" (Lefebvre, 1991, p. 26). Doreen Massey (2005) also argues that space is socially constructed and notes that "if space is indeed the product of interrelations, then it must be predicated upon the existence of plurality [...], always under construction" (p. 9). Within this context, feminist theory compels us to ask: whose experiences, whose bodies, whose mobility are legitimized and restricted within that space?

The relationship between gender and space has long been a central concern in both feminist and literary theory, as spatial divisions have historically been used to enforce and reproduce gender roles. In the 19th century, women were largely confined to the private sphere. As Carole Pateman argues in *The Sexual Contract* (1988), "what it means to be an 'individual', a maker of contracts and civilly free, is revealed by the subjection of women within the private sphere" (p. 21). This foundational oppression birthed a rallying cry, which was "the personal is political" by Carol Hanisch in 1969. The association of femininity with domestic space persisted throughout the 20th century, sustaining spatial and symbolic boundaries that limited women's access to public agency. The domestic sphere was idealized as a space of comfort and feminine fulfillment. Betty Friedan critically addresses this contradiction in *The Feminine Mystique* (1963), observing how modern suburban homes were designed in ways that eliminated solitude and intensified the demands of care, noting, "there are no true walls or doors; the woman in the beautiful electronic kitchen is never separated from her children. She need never feel alone for a minute, need never be by herself" (1977, p. 235). With the rise of third-wave feminism in the 1990s, feminist thought further emphasized race, class, and gender, challenging universalist notions of womanhood. Among these voices, bell hooks (1984), who made the experiences of Black women visible within feminist discourse, reclaimed the margin as a space of resistance. She underscored the importance of resistant spaces, arguing that "once woman-centered space exists, it can be maintained only if women remain convinced that it is the only place where they can be self-realized and free" (hooks, 1984, p. 27). In the wake of these debates, fourth-wave feminists during the 2010s turned to digital platforms, most notably Twitter (now X), to expose how online spaces maintain patriarchal control and create new arenas for resistance. Hashtag campaigns such as #HeforShe (2014), #SayHerName (2014), #MeToo (2017), #TimesUp (2018), and #LetHerSpeak (2018) transformed social media into contemporary "digital billboards," where women could publicly name injustice, abuse, violence, harassment, discrimination, and reclaim visibility as a form of political power. Just as these hashtags make visible the overlooked injustices women face and assert a demand for female acclaim via digital manifesto, the billboards in *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017) provide a similar embodiment of resistance in physical space.

As feminist movements increasingly claimed space, online and offline, they mirrored a deeper insight, underlining that space itself is shaped by power. Linda McDowell (1999) explains that the way our environments are organized often reflects and sustains gender hierarchies (p. 12). In many cultures, certain spaces, such as the home, the kitchen, and the nursery, have traditionally been considered feminine spaces. As a result, women who step out of these so-called spaces are perceived as a threat in the patriarchal order or are considered dangerous outside these spaces. Doreen Massey (1994) draws attention to a prevalent argument in this context, arguing, "women lead more local lives than do men," and this "clearly relates to the public/private division" (p. 9). Patriarchy also deprives women of equal access to public space. McDowell (1999) points out that even in courts, "through the judgments made in cases of rape

and harassment, judges often argue that women should remain indoors for their own protection" (p. 150). By doing so, the system justifies the idea that women have no rights in the public sphere, while claiming to protect them from its dangers.

McDowell extends these spatial discussions, exploring how gender influences and is influenced by spatial practices. Since women's presence outside is seen as a threat to patriarchy, women who violate the norm are blamed. According to McDowell (1999), patriarchal law often treats a woman being "out too late" or "in the wrong place" as justification for the violence committed against her and "the element of fault, it is implied, is on her part rather than on the part of the man who attacked her" (pp. 150-151). In support of this view, Doreen Massey (1994) emphasizes that women's presence in cities has been questioned throughout history, claiming that "almost from the beginning, the presence of women in cities, and particularly in city streets, has been questioned, and the controlling and surveillance aspects of city life have always been directed particularly at women" (p. 167). This view reflects a deeper mindset about where women supposedly belong. As McDowell (1999) explains, "the idea that women have a particular place is the basis not only of the social organization of a whole range of institutions from the family to the workplace, from the shopping mall to political institutions, but also is an essential feature of Western Enlightenment thought" (p. 12).

While space and place often carry expectations and rules, and for women, these usually involve judgment and limitation, many feminist thinkers see the spatial zones also as sites of resistance. Feminist geographer Gillian Rose (1993) argues that the feminist subject must embrace the value of differences that dominant social structures tend to exclude. As she notes, "the project of the subject of feminism is to comprehend the 'positivity of otherness' and resistance to the exclusions of dominant subjectivities is articulated through spatial images" (p. 150). For Rose (1993), resistance takes shape within this space, which can further distort or redirect the dominant gaze. In this space, the feminist subject finds itself in a state of contradiction as well. In Rose's terms (1993), it is precisely this contradiction that compels the subject to resist, to "imagine the position of being both prisoner and exile, both within and without [and] locate a place which is both crucial to, yet also denied by, the Same" (p. 159).

Cixous' *écriture féminine*, at this point, radicalizes the spatial resistance described by Rose and McDowell. Her insistence that women "write through their bodies" (1976, p. 886) to "shatter the framework of institutions" (1976, p. 887) illuminates the protagonist, Mildred's act of using billboards as both textual and spatial uprising. In this way, space transforms from a site of restriction into one where new social orders and different ways of belonging can be created. These spatial theories, then, provide the groundwork for this article's analysis of *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017), where the protagonist, Mildred, uses spatial tactics to take up public space and challenge the gendered boundaries that attempt to silence her.

MARTIN MCDONAGH AND THE MAKING OF *THREE BILLBOARDS*

Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri (2017) is the third feature-length film written and directed by Martin McDonagh, an award-winning, London-born Irish-British playwright and filmmaker whose career originated in the world of theatre. Before transitioning to cinema, McDonagh earned acclaim for his provocative and violent stage plays such as *The Beauty Queen of Leenane* (1996), *The Lieutenant of Inishmore* (2001), and *The Pillowman* (2003), which were recognized for their dark humor, satiric language, moral dilemmas, while the violence, as Lonergan (2012) notes, is "not caused by 'evil', but [...] by the 'texture' of his characters' lives" (p. 14). According to Konárková, his themes coincided with a period when the European audience "for the macabre and the grotesque combined with extreme violence and vulgarity has

been whetted by 'in-yer-face theatre'² (p. 229). His theatrical background continues to shape his films through dialogue-centered storytelling and the use of violence and dark humor. However, McDonagh has openly admitted his deeper affinity for cinema, stating, "when I started out I was very vociferously against theatre or what I saw theatre as being, so I tried to make my plays the opposite of that – something a bit more cinematic. I'm a film kid so I'll never have the same love of theatre as I do of movies. It's just the way I was brought up" (as cited in Stolworthy, 2017, para. 9). Following his distinguished films, *In Bruges* (2008) and *Seven Psychopaths* (2012), McDonagh shifts his focus in *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017) from Irish and British male antiheroes to a female-driven narrative of maternal rage and systemic injustice.

The film received widespread appreciation and continued winning multiple awards, including two Academy Awards in 2018, which were "Best Actress for Frances McDormand" and "Best Supporting Actor for Sam Rockwell." Set in a fictional town called "Ebbing," supposedly located in Missouri, the story centers on Mildred Hayes, a grieving mother who rents three roadside billboards to publicly challenge the local police's failure to solve her daughter's rape and murder. Reflecting on the development of the script, McDonagh himself stated, "I wanted to write a very strong female lead because the other two films [didn't have that] at all. Her character popped out the moment I decided that it was a mother in my story and, to a degree, the film started writing itself after that" (as cited in Stolworthy, 2017, para. 14), letting the story unfold from a mother's perspective and resistance. As Mildred's fight becomes the town's fight, the story also offers a deeper look at how the town's people respond to pain, blame, and anger, adding to female identity and resistance in the film.

Critiques on the film explore how the character of Mildred Hayes is transformed through gender, violence, and representation of space through different theoretical frameworks. For instance, according to Vassilev (2024), Mildred is a figure who does not back down despite facing almost all segments of the town and being subjected to intense threats, exclusion, and violence (p. 108), as she "succeeds precisely because she manages to unite her masculine and feminine sides" (p. 115). Similarly, Ferguson (2019) interprets Mildred's rage through Jack Halberstam's concept of "female masculinity," suggesting that Mildred adopts hypermasculine, violent behavior to demonstrate that "women, too, can use violence to terrorize others" (p. 34). Correlatively, Haque (2019) conceptualizes Mildred's critique of patriarchal institutions through billboards as "discursive spaces" (p. 27) and claims that these billboards produce a counter-discourse against a corrupt system and politicize the female subject's relationship with space (p. 27). This article, in turn, approaches Mildred's defiance through the lens of feminist spatial frameworks and interprets her use of the billboards as a spatial and discursive act of resistance.

MARTIN MCDONAGH'S *THREE BILLBOARDS OUTSIDE EBBING, MISSOURI* (2017) THROUGH THE THEORIES OF SPACE, PLACE, AND FEMALE IDENTITY

"Looks like we got a war on our hands."
— *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017)

In *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017), space is not singular in meaning. The road near the Drinkwater where Mildred plants her message, the police station that guards the town's authority, her home where grief escalates, and the main street, which becomes a battleground, are all examples of spaces of conflict and sites of female resistance. Among these, the road where the billboards stand, initially an ignored zone, becomes a key space for Mildred, for it is only in

² The term is coined by writers in the UK during the 1990s. It describes a tendency to write plays that include elements such as violence, sexuality, drugs, and murder (Sierz, 2001).

this central space that her resistance becomes visible and exposes the town's silence. In contrast, the police station, as the embodiment of injustice and patriarchal state power, functions as an "enemy stronghold" which Mildred constantly violates and confronts directly. Her attachment to this space is fueled by her sense of obligation to disturb and hold the system accountable within its own territory. Meanwhile, Mildred's home, which traditionally should serve as a private sphere, is instead a site of internal warfare. It has become the scene of trauma, shaped by her daughter's final moments and Mildred's overwhelming guilt. Ultimately, Mildred's deep, often painful but never submissive attachment to these spaces stems from their tie to Angela's death, the town's injustice, and Mildred's changing identity. These physical locations have thus become both the cause and the instrument of her grief, anger, and relentless struggle.

From the very beginning, the fictional town of Ebbing allows Mildred Hayes to carry the emotional weight of her daughter's murder. Ebbing, then, is not so much a geographic location as it is a landscape defined more by grief and anger, where "the three old billboards [stand] alone like tombstones on the dusty road" (McDonagh, 2017a, p. 1). This provincial town reflects the mentality of a typical small American town: traditional and bound by social norms. As Raymond Williams suggests in *The Country and the City* (2013), "on the country has gathered the idea of a natural way of life: of peace, innocence, and simple virtue. [...] [Yet] on the country [has also] gathered [...] the idea of backwardness, ignorance, limitation" (p. 9). Ebbing initially embodies this duality. It is precisely at the heart of this duality that Mildred Hayes is positioned as a figure of resistance who rejects the traditional role of "womanhood" in the small town of Ebbing.

The contrast between repression and resistance is also visible inside Mildred's private space, her house. Angela's room represents one of the intimate spots within the broader concept of home, serving as a physical space, clearly divided from the rest of the house. The Nirvana poster and guitar in the room reflect her daughter's personality, interests, and dreams. Yet, for Mildred, this room has taken on a deeper emotional meaning, carrying the burden of the past with her daughter's rape and murder. Similar to Tuan's conceptualization of "pauses," the hallway to Angela's room includes "pauses along the way," such as the kitchen, which functions as a critical "pause" in the movement of female entrapment and resilience. While it is a stopping point that prevents Mildred from directly confronting the images of her tragic past, it also offers her a transitory space to connect to the memories of her daughter. In one scene, as she walks down the hallway, she pauses in front of Angela's room, where a red "DANGER" (McDonagh, 2017b, 33:36) sign, which was once a sign of teenage attitude, is now a quiet reminder of her absence, still hanging on the door. A few moments later, she hesitates again and recalls their final argument in the kitchen, ending with Angela shouting, "I hope I get raped on the way" (McDonagh, 2017b, 35:04) and Mildred bitterly responding, "I hope you get raped too" (McDonagh, 2017b, 35:07). This flashback interrupts her movement, turning both the kitchen and hallway into a site of maternal guilt and unresolved grief.

While home represents a deeply personal and emotional space for Mildred, the public spaces in Ebbing demonstrate the broader institutional structures that she must confront. This tension appears in the film as the female protagonist navigates public spaces. Yet, her presence is constantly shaped or constrained by social pressures in state institutions, such as the police station. When she puts up the billboards criticizing the local police, her act faces institutional resistance from police officers such as Dixon and Willoughby, along with social pressure from members of the community. She is verbally abused by her ex-husband and met with disapproval from others in the town, especially the local priest. The police station appears early in the film as a place of conflict and failure. However, it carries a strong masculine tone and becomes one

of the main locations to which Mildred repeatedly returns, challenging figures of authority, especially Chief Willoughby (starring Woody Harrelson), the head of the police station, and Officer Dixon (starring Sam Rockwell). Officer Dixon, who changes from a villain to a hero, embodies masculine control through his relaxed and confident behavior in the police station, putting his feet up on the desk, moving around easily, reading comic books (McDonagh, 2017b, 23:48), and listening to ABBA's "Chiquitita" while working (McDonagh, 2017b, 54:52).

For Mildred, however, the police station becomes a space where her demands for justice are dismissed and her sense of agency is undermined. In Henri Lefebvre's terms, the police station exemplifies a conceived space, run by the dominant forces of law, order, and patriarchal authority. In Althusser's (2014) terms, on the other hand, it operates as an "Ideological State Apparatus" (ISA), a term he uses to describe institutions such as schools, armies, churches, and police stations that function by ideology (p. 244), and also as part of the Repressive State Apparatus (RSA), which "function predominantly by repression" (p. 244). Following this, it can be argued that the female protagonist utilizes Althusser's (2014) insight that both systems "ensure the reproduction of the relations of production" (p. 1), exposing how the station perpetuates racial violence under ideological cover. In one of the most confrontational moments, during her interrogation, Mildred turns to Dixon and says: "so how's it all going in the n**torturing business, Dixon?" (McDonagh, 2017b, 27:58). This moment, among others, breaks the usual image of the station as a perceived space, where Mildred openly challenges the authority of Dixon by shouting, "hey, fuckhead! [...] get over here" (McDonagh, 2017b, 42:03-42:12). It is at this moment that, through Mildred's repeated confrontations and resistance, the space is transformed into a perceived one. Her words literally interrupt the station's formal atmosphere, prompting the desk sergeant to respond, "you do not allow a member of the public to call you a fuckhead in the station house!" (McDonagh, 2017b, 42:21-42:22). If we recall McDowell's argument that public and private spheres are not natural categories but are constructed through gendered power relations, then Mildred's presence in this male-dominated institutional space and her refusal to conform to the expectations of passive and private grief, exemplifies a direct challenge to those spatial norms.

In contrast to the confined and masculinized interior of the Ebbing police station, the open roads of Ebbing seem to offer Mildred a different kind of spatial possibility. Initially, the town's vast open roads suggest a sense of freedom. Nonetheless, this impression begins to shift as soon as Mildred rents the long-abandoned billboard panels from a local advertising agency and displays her messages along the roadside. Although the road is a public and constantly moving space, it becomes a literal and metaphorical pause for Mildred. As Tuan (1977) observes, "abstract space, lacking significance other than strangeness, becomes concrete place, filled with meaning" (p. 199). Mildred's billboards exactly mark this transformation from undifferentiated space to a personally and politically charged place.

In American cultural narratives, roads have often been imagined as masculine realms where men seek freedom, rebellion, or self-discovery. These narratives are deeply intertwined with the legacy of the 19th century American frontier myth, which idealized westward expansion as a masculine pursuit of freedom and conquest, as Ganser (2009) has noted, "the parallels between the 19th century frontier myth and the construction of the American road genre as a masculine territory in the second half of the 20th century are neither negligible nor coincidental" (p. 84). Women, therefore, are usually portrayed as endangered in such settings. Judith Butler (2015) points out that "if there is a body in the public sphere, it is masculine and unsupported, presumptively free to create, but not itself created. And the body in the private sphere is female, ageing, foreign, or childish, and pre-political" (p. 2). Against this backdrop, Mildred's presence

on the roadside disrupts these norms. She does not pass through the road like male wanderers, but stands still and insists on being seen. Rather than challenging the “masculine road myth,” Mildred subverts it, interrupting the flow of the road and changing its motion so that no one can pass without noticing the billboards. Through this act, she transforms a traditionally masculine space into a feminist symbol of protest.

While Tuan's earlier remarks helped interpret the road as a personal pause for Mildred, his further ideas also allow us to consider how the billboards capture public attention in shaping the space. He explains that place emerges through perception shaped by what catches our attention and how we respond to it. He writes, “place can be defined in a variety of ways. Among them is the place where a stable object catches our attention. As we look at a panoramic scene, our eyes pause at points of interest. Each pause is time enough to create an image of place that looms large momentarily in our view” (Tuan, 1977, p. 161). In this sense, the billboards function precisely in the same way as stable objects determine meaning and power. Their content, “How Come, Chief Willoughby?” “And Still No Arrests?” and “Raped While Dying” (McDonagh, 2017b, 06:58) demand attention and transform the roadside into a symbolic site of social unrest by carving Angela's violated body into the town's physical landscape. The billboards' liminal location is also critical. Situated on a desolate highway, neither urban center nor private domain, they materialize Cixous' (1976) call to “to break up, to destroy; and to foresee the unforeseeable” (p. 875). This integration positions Mildred as a Cixousian heroine who uses spatial and linguistic defiance to “inscribe the breath of the whole woman” (Cixous, 1976, p. 880), exemplifying how “the repressed of culture” (Cixous, 1976, p. 878) can reclaim space through embodied resistance. The billboards, on this basis, embody Cixous' (1976) claim that women “put [them]selves into the text—as into the world and into history” (p. 875). The billboards in the film function as powerful means of *écriture féminine*; especially when the local dentist tries to pull her tooth without anesthesia and uses his authority to punish her resistance, Mildred retaliates by piercing the dentist's finger with a dental tool and then spitting on his face (McDonagh, 2017b, 25:51-26:54). In that moment, staring down the punishment of the male gaze, that is, the dentist's, she *becomes* Medusa, and her spit, along with her strike, *is* her laugh.

Aware of the legal and social consequences of her actions, the female protagonist further ensures, as Jordan (2019) points out that “what is displayed on the three billboards contains nothing libellous and nothing defamatory, cross-checking with the local advertising agent, Red Welby (Caleb Landry Jones) [wanting to] remain within the limits of the law” (p. 105). Yet beyond their function as visual markers, these billboards also represent a turning point in Mildred's spatial journey. Drawing on Tuan's (1977) categorization of place as a sequence of home, wayside stations, and the goal itself (p. 180), Mildred's movements become part of a journey in which her home is where the trauma begins, the road with the billboards becomes a temporary but powerful stop, and justice is the goal she hopes to reach.

Within this framework, Massey's arguments that space is socially constructed through interrelations (2005, p. 9) and the constant questioning of women's presence in public spaces (1994, p. 167) resurface concretely in Mildred's resistance. Staying within the law does not mean Mildred accepts the roles expected of her. She refuses to stay silent or invisible, as women are often expected to do. Instead, she chooses to be visible in the public sphere rather than retreating home and mourning silently. Thus, she directly opposes the male-dominated order of the town, with the placement of the billboards being her first physical and symbolic intervention against this patriarchal order. In one of the early scenes, she gives an interview to reporters behind the three rented billboards, directly addressing the town's silence and the police department's neglect: “seems to me the local police department is too busy torturing black folks to be bothered

doing anything about solving actual crime. I thought these billboards might concentrate their minds some" (McDonagh, 2017b, 13:14-13:24).

Mildred's insistence on visibility extends into the domestic space as well. When Chief Willoughby visits her at home to explain that the DNA found at the crime scene does not match any known profile, Mildred responds with impatience, saying, "the time it's took you to come out here whining like a bitch, Willoughby, some other poor girl's probably being butchered right now" (McDonagh, 2017b, 15:47-15:52). In line with Gillian Rose's (1993) argument that feminist subjects occupy positions "both within and without" dominant spatial borders (p. 159), Mildred's resistance continues from this position. A few scenes later, a different kind of authority enters Mildred's home, this time, not from the police, but from the church. The local priest urges Mildred to remove the billboards, subtly implying that her protest disturbs the peace. Mildred listens, then cuts through the priest's moral superiority, saying, "you joined the gang, you're culpable. And when a person is culpable to altar-boy-fucking, or any kind of boy-fucking, because I know you guys didn't really narrow that down, then you kind of forfeit the right to come into my house and say anything about me or my life or my daughter or my billboards" (McDonagh, 2017b, 22:25-22:51). Mildred's actions within home and her relations with masculine authorities also show how political the distinction between public and private space that Massey (2005) mentions for women (p. 9). By bringing her public demands into her private space, Mildred ensures that the house becomes a part of the public struggle rather than a private refuge as well. Mildred's anger builds throughout the film, and it comes to a head when she sets the police station on fire, thinking that the officers were the ones who burned her billboards:

As Mildred burns down the police station, slow-moving imagery and the words of a now-dead Willoughby ("Hate never solved nothing. But calm did. And thought did") contrast uneasily with an awesome display of uninhibited wrath, of a primal need to act rather than be acted upon, to assert something, anything in a place where one's assertions fall dumb in the face of cosmic, uncontrollable forces (Fernelius, 2019, p. 226)

Based on this example, it can be argued that Mildred speaks from within the role of a mother, yet also defies norms by acting as a rebel. In doing so, she alters the meaning of the space around her, as the police station is no longer seen as a symbol of authority and protection, and her home is no longer a private space.

Mildred's challenge to the silence of the police is not only metaphorical, but also visualized through her actions. According to McDowell (1999), the bodies are shaped by the spaces they move through, and how the body is perceived depends on where it is:

The body is the place, the location or site, if you like, of the individual, with more or less impermeable boundaries between one body and another. While bodies are undoubtedly material, possessing a range of characteristics such as shape and size and so inevitably taking up space, the ways in which bodies are presented to and seen by others vary according to the spaces and places in which they find themselves (p. 34).

In the film, as Mildred's body often navigates across public spaces such as the police station, the advertising agency, and the road, her body carries a certain presence and identity. When she sets up the billboards, her bodily presence by the roadside turns her into a part of the town's landscape. Her actions are continuously observed by passersby, residents, and police officers, making her body and movements subject to surveillance and evaluation. Even while Father Montgomery's remark that "but the town also knows what kind of a man William Willoughby is. And the town is dead set against these billboards of yours" (McDonagh, 2017b, 20:27-20:35) exemplifies the very process Massey (2005) describes, where women's presence in public space

is constantly questioned (p. 9), Mildred's body standing by the billboards makes this presence impossible to ignore. It even disturbs the church's image of how a woman should occupy space, which is reinforced when the Father tells her, "if you hadn't stopped coming to church, you'd have a little bit more understanding of the depth of people's feelings" (McDonagh, 2017b, 20:39-20:45). In this context, her body becomes, in Grosz's (1995) terms, a sign to be read within systems of meaning that discipline female visibility (p. 51).

Ultimately, in Martin McDonagh's *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017), the female protagonist, Mildred Hayes, strategically utilizes various public and private spaces within the town as sites of female resistance and acclaim, most notably by employing her billboards as a means of seeking justice for her late daughter. Through the billboards she displays on a neglected roadside, Mildred brings her private pain into the public sphere, forcing the town community to confront what has long been ignored. Further, she challenges the police station, an emblem of male authority, through both verbal and physical actions. Additionally, within her home, she resists traditional social expectations by refusing to conform to the passive mourning role often expected of women. Therefore, by being visibly present in male-dominated spaces, she challenges power structures and reshapes them through her agency. Fundamentally, Mildred's strategies bring into focus the questions of who determines women's "place" and by what means, exposing the political relations of space and place.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, this study has analyzed Mildred Hayes' quest for justice following the rape and murder of her daughter in Martin McDonagh's *Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri* (2017). The analysis has been framed through the lens of feminist spatial theory, with reference to the works of feminist geographers Doreen Massey and Linda McDowell, feminist philosopher and writer Helene Cixous, and spatial theorists Yi-Fu Tuan and Henri Lefebvre. It has further centered on the visibility of women's bodies, anger, and voice in the public sphere, with a focus on the symbolic and spatial function of the billboards. Adopting a feminist perspective has been essential for understanding how the film reveals the ways in which women's experiences are often silenced in patriarchal spaces, and how Mildred's actions challenge this by making her pain and anger visible and public. By directly intervening in spaces shaped by patriarchal power, it has been shown that Mildred asserts her presence through bodily and verbal acts, redefining the boundaries of female agency in the public sphere. Thus, the billboards in the film have been reinterpreted as a written form of action and a means of transforming space. In this respect, the study offers a distinctive perspective by showing how feminist spatial theory helps explain the ways female subjectivity resists spatial limitations and reclaims agency within the cinematic space.

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